

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP4 – WP Technical Framework

D4.2 First version of the Framework for quality benchmarking

Lead contributor	Clair Blacketer (1/12 – Erasmus UMC/Janssen)
Lead contributor email	mblacke@its.jnj.com
Other contributors	Michel van Speybroeck (12, Janssen) Maxim Moinat (6, The Hyve)
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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland
Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) developed as part of EHDEN Work Package 4 provides a comprehensive, customizable, and transparent way to both evaluate and communicate the quality of an OMOP CDM instance. It provides both the code to run data quality checks against an OMOP CDM instance, as well as visualising the results in a web application.

The data quality checks were organised using the widely accepted Kahn Framework for data quality. This groups the checks types in categories: Conformance, Completeness and Plausibility. Each category has one or more subcategories and are evaluated in two contexts: Validation and Verification.

Each SME and data partner will be expected to run the Data Quality Dashboard on the data at their site once it is converted to the OMOP CDM. Initially it can be used to assess whether OMOP Standards such as primary key constraints and concept domain restrictions are being followed. Thinking specifically of the EHDEN federated network, providing an interactive data quality report for each participating site will provide evidence not only that OMOP specifications were followed correctly but also to demonstrate that the necessary due diligence was done to ensure that the data are of research quality.

We believe the DQD is a strong foundation for data quality reporting, and a key tool to ensure confidence in the evidence generated through the EHDEN federated network.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document reports on the development of a systematic approach to data quality assessment of data converted to the OMOP CDM, delivered by the European Health Data and Evidence Framework (EHDEN).

The conversion of source data to the OMOP CDM is a multi-step process which requires a team with diverse skills and knowledge. Data quality checking is required at every step of the process. During the mapping implementation this can be achieved with unit tests to test individual pieces of logic. After the transformation has been completed, the data quality can be checked by running an assessment. In previous years the OHDSI community used a tool called ‘Achilles’, that both characterized the data in the OMOP CDM and ran a set of data quality checks. However, the number of data quality checks were limited, not customizable and it was difficult to find the cause of a check failing.

The definition of data quality is put as ‘a measure that validates the actual behaviour of a “component” against its original intended characteristics of use in operations, decision-making, and planning’[1]. This means that a data source can be of high quality for one purpose and of low quality for another. In addition, the same data quality metric can mean different things for different data sources. E.g. missing race information is inherent in some data sources as this is not always captured.

In the context of EHDEN and the wider OHDSI community, a new data quality tool was developed; the Data Quality Dashboard. This dashboard incorporates more data quality metrics than Achilles and reports detailed information on failed data quality metrics. The output can be tailored for each data source to make sure relevant metrics are captured.

2. DATA QUALITY DASHBOARD

2.1 Motivation

The goal of the Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) project was to design and develop an open-source tool to expose and evaluate observational data quality in response to the needs of global regulatory agencies.

2.2 Development

At a high-level this project consisted of creating a way to run a series of data quality checks against an OMOP CDM instance. The vision was to create an application that would systematically run the checks, evaluate the checks against some pre-specified threshold, and then communicate what was done in a transparent and easily understandable way.

Beginning with the checks themselves, the Kahn Framework¹ was chosen to organize those covered by the tool as it is widely accepted as the terminology to use when discussing data quality. Under this framework checks fall into categories, subcategories, and contexts.

As described by Kahn et al, there are three categories into which data quality checks can be organized: conformance, completeness and plausibility. Each category can be interpreted within two different contexts that represent strategies for assessing data quality:

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5051581/>

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- Verification relates to how well data conform to local knowledge, metadata descriptions, and system assumptions.
- Validation relates to how well data align with external benchmarks with expectations derived from known true standards.

In the next sections we will describe each category and its subcategories as defined by Kahn et al. with implementation examples from the OMOP CDM in each of the two contexts. Many of the examples given below have been incorporated into version 1 of the Data Quality Dashboard, though some are still in development.

2.2.1 Kahn Framework for Data Quality

Category 1: Conformance

Conformance focuses on DQ checks that describe the compliance of the representation of data against internal or external formatting, relational, or computational definitions. Typically, the “data dictionary” describes the expected conformance values and whether there are internal formatting constraints imposed or if an external standard was used to represent the data values. Conformance can be divided into three subcategories: value conformance, relational conformance, and computational conformance.

Subcategory 1: Value Conformance

Determines if recorded data elements are in agreement with the data architecture as expected or as described in the data dictionary or external standards. For example, here is how value conformance can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
Data values conform to internal constraints	GENDER_SOURCE_VALUE is only one ASCII character as is stated in the native data dictionary
Data values conform to allowable values or ranges	GENDER_CONCEPT_ID only has values 8532 or 8507
VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
Data values conform to representational constraints based on external values	Values for ETHNICITY_CONCEPT_ID conform to US OMB standards

Subcategory 2: Relational Conformance

Determines if recorded data elements are in agreement with the structural constraints imposed by the physical database structures. In this category are conformance to primary key and foreign key relationships and nullability constraints. For example, here is how relational conformance can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
Data values conform to relational constraints	PERSON_ID links to other tables as described in the CDM specifications
Unique (key) data values are not duplicated	A VISIT_OCCURRENCE_ID is assigned uniquely to a healthcare encounter
Changes to the data model or data model versioning	Version 6.0 includes DEATH_DATETIME in the PERSON table

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VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
Data values conform to relational constraints based on external standards	Each record in the PERSON table has a non-NULL value in the PERSON_ID field.

Subcategory 3: Computational Conformance

Determines if computed values yield the intended results either within a data set (Verification) or between data sets (Validation). For example, here is how computational conformance can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
Computed values conform to computational or programming specifications	Database- and hand-calculated Body Mass Index (BMI) values using height and weight available on the same day are identical

VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
Computed results based on published algorithms yield values that match validation values provided by external source	Computed BMI percentiles yield identical values compared to BMI percentiles provided by the World Health Organization

Category 2: Completeness

Completeness in the sense of data quality is solely focused on quantifying missingness, or the absence of data. This category does not reference the structure or plausibility of the data, which is handled by the Conformance and Plausibility categories. For example, here is how completeness can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
The absence of data values at a single moment in time agrees with local or common expectations	The PERSON.PERSON_ID field has no missing values
The absence of data values measured over time agrees with local or common expectations	VISIT.VISIT_END_DATE is not present in an outpatient database where it is understood that all visits are one day in length

VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
The absence of data values measured over time agrees with trusted reference standards or external knowledge.	A drop in condition codes matches implementation of new condition vocabulary.

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Category 3: Plausibility

Plausibility seeks to determine the believability or truthfulness of data values. Plausibility focuses on actual values as a representation of a real-world object or conceptual construct by examining the distribution and density of values or by comparing multiple values that have an expected relationship to each other.

Subcategory 1: Uniqueness Plausibility

Determines if objects appear multiple times where they should not be duplicated. For example, here is how Uniqueness Plausibility can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
Data values that identify a single object are not duplicated	Unique PERSON_SOURCE_VALUES are not assigned multiple PERSON_IDS

VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
Data values that identify a single object in an external source are not duplicated	A unique national physician identifier does not refer to multiple physicians

Subcategory 2: Atemporal Plausibility

Determines if observed data values, distributions, or densities agree with “common” knowledge or with external sources that are deemed to be trusted or are a relative gold standard. For example, here is how Atemporal Plausibility can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
Data values and distributions agree with an internal measurement or local knowledge	Height and weight values are positive
Data values and distributions for independent measurements of the same fact are in agreement	Serum glucose and finger-stick glucose values are similar
Logical constraints between values agree with local or common knowledge	Sex values agree with sex-specific contexts (pregnancy, prostate cancer)
Values of repeated measurement of the same fact show expected variability	Height values are similar when take by two separate nurses within the same facility using the same equipment

VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
Data values and distributions (including subgroup distributions) agree with trusted reference standards or external knowledge	HbA1c values from a hospital and reference lab are statistically similar under the same conditions
Similar values for identical measurements are obtained from two independent databases representing the same observations with equal credibility	Diabetes condition and procedure code distributions are similar between two databases serving similar populations

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Two dependent databases (e.g., database 1 abstracted from database 2) yield similar values for identical variables	Recorded YEAR_OF_BIRTH is consistent between EHR and registry data for the same patient
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Subcategory 3: Temporal Plausibility

Determines if time-varying change values as expected based on known temporal properties or if time-varying relationships hold across related fields. For example, here is how Temporal Plausibility can be interpreted through the lens of verification and validation:

VERIFICATION	
Definition	Example
Observed or derived values conform to expected temporal properties	VISIT_START_DATE occurs before VISIT_END_DATE
Sequences of values that represent state transitions conform to expected properties	Date of an initial immunization precedes date of a booster immunization
Measures of data value density against a time-oriented denominator are expected based on internal knowledge	Similar counts of patient observations between extraction-transform-load cycles

VALIDATION	
Definition	Example
Observed or derived values have similar temporal properties across one or more external comparators or gold standards	Length of stay by outpatient procedure is similar for similar populations in different databases
Sequences of values that represent state transitions are similar to external comparators or gold standards	Immunization sequences match the WHO recommendations
Measures of data value density against a time-oriented denominator are expected based on external knowledge	Counts of emergency department room visits by month shows spike during flu season that are similar to local health department reports

2.2.2 DQ Checks

Using the Kahn framework as the way to organize ideas, the Data Quality Dashboard takes a systematic-based approach to running data quality checks. Instead of writing thousands of individual checks, we use what we call “data quality check types”. These “check types” are more general, parameterized data quality checks into which OMOP tables, fields, and concepts can be substituted to represent a singular data quality idea. For example, one check type might be written as

The number and percent of records with a value in the @cdmFieldName field of the @cdmTableName table less than @plausibleValueLow.

This would be considered an atemporal plausibility verification check because we are looking for implausibly low values in some field based on internal knowledge. We can use this check type to substitute in values for @cdmFieldName, @cdmTableName, and @plausibleValueLow to create a unique data quality check. If we apply it to PERSON.YEAR_OF_BIRTH here is how that might look:

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The number and percent of records with a value in the **year_of_birth** field of the **PERSON** table less than **1850**.

And, since it is parameterized, we can similarly apply it to DRUG_EXPOSURE.days_supply:

The number and percent of records with a value in the **days_supply** field of the **DRUG_EXPOSURE** table less than **0**.

Version 1 of the tool² includes 20 different check types organized into Kahn contexts and categories. Additionally, each data quality check type is considered either a table check, field check, or concept-level check. Table-level checks are those evaluating the table at a high-level without reference to individual fields, or those that span multiple event tables. These include checks making sure required tables are present or that at least some of the people in the PERSON table have records in the event tables. Field-level checks are those related to specific fields in a table. The majority of the check types in version 1 are field-level checks. These include checks evaluating primary key relationship and those investigating if the concepts in a field conform to the specified domain. Concept-level checks are related to individual concepts. These include checks looking for gender-specific concepts in persons of the wrong gender and plausible values for measurement-unit pairs. The below table lists all check types, the check level (table, field, concept), a description of the check, and Kahn category and context it fits into.

Throughout the development of the DQD, meetings were held both to discuss the design and implementation. Stakeholders were encouraged to weigh in and the final check types were chosen and implemented based on their feedback.

Check Level	Check Name	Check Description	Kahn Context	Kahn Category	Kahn Sub-category
TABLE	measurePerson Completeness	The number and percent of persons in the CDM that do not have at least one record in the @cdmTableName table	Validation	Completeness	
FIELD	cdmField	A yes or no value indicating if all fields are present in the @cdmTableName table as expected based on the specification.	Verification	Conformance	Relational
FIELD	isRequired	The number and percent of records with a NULL value in the @cdmFieldName of the @cdmTableName that is considered not nullable.	Validation	Conformance	Relational
FIELD	cdmDatatype	A yes or no value indicating if the @cdmFieldName in the @cdmTableName is the expected data type based on the specification.	Verification	Conformance	Value
FIELD	isPrimaryKey	The number and percent of records that have a duplicate value in the @cdmFieldName field of the @cdmTableName.	Verification	Conformance	Relational
FIELD	isForeignKey	The number and percent of records that have a value in the @cdmFieldName field in the	Verification	Conformance	Relational

² <https://github.com/ohdsi/dataqualitydashboard>

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Check Level	Check Name	Check Description	Kahn Context	Kahn Category	Kahn Sub-category
		<i>@cdmTableName table that does not exist in the @fkTableName table.</i>			
FIELD	fkDomain	<i>The number and percent of records that have a value in the @cdmFieldName field in the @cdmTableName table that do not conform to the @fkDomain domain.</i>	Verification	Conformance	Value
FIELD	fkClass	<i>The number and percent of records that have a value in the @cdmFieldName field in the @cdmTableName table that do not conform to the @fkClass class.</i>	Verification	Conformance	Computational
FIELD	isStandardValid Concept	<i>The number and percent of records that do not have a standard, valid concept in the @cdmFieldName field in the @cdmTableName table.</i>	Verification	Conformance	
FIELD	measureValue Completeness	<i>The number and percent of records with a NULL value in the @cdmFieldName of the @cdmTableName.</i>	Verification	Completeness	
FIELD	standardConcept RecordCompleteness	<i>The number and percent of records with a value of 0 in the standard concept field @cdmFieldName in the @cdmTableName table.</i>	Verification	Completeness	
FIELD	sourceConcept RecordCompleteness	<i>The number and percent of records with a value of 0 in the source concept field @cdmFieldName in the @cdmTableName table.</i>	Verification	Completeness	
FIELD	sourceValueCompleteness	<i>The number and percent of distinct source values in the @cdmFieldName field of the @cdmTableName table mapped to 0.</i>	Verification	Completeness	
FIELD	plausibleValue Low	<i>The number and percent of records with a value in the @cdmFieldName field of the @cdmTableName table less than @plausibleValueLow.</i>	Verification	Plausibility	Atemporal
FIELD	plausibleValue High	<i>The number and percent of records with a value in the @cdmFieldName field of the @cdmTableName table greater than @plausibleValueHigh.</i>	Verification	Plausibility	Atemporal
FIELD	Plausible TemporalAfter	<i>The number and percent of records with a value in the @cdmFieldName field of the @cdmTableName table that occurs prior to the date in the @plausibleTemporalAfterFieldName field of the @plausibleTemporalAfterTableName table.</i>	Verification	Plausibility	Temporal
FIELD	Plausible DuringLife	<i>If yes, the number and percent of records with a date value in the @cdmFieldName field of the</i>	Verification	Plausibility	Temporal

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Check Level	Check Name	Check Description	Kahn Context	Kahn Category	Kahn Sub-category
		<i>@cdmTableName table that occurs after death.</i>			
CONCEPT	plausibleValue Low	<i>For the combination of CONCEPT_ID @conceptId (@conceptName) and UNIT_CONCEPT_ID @unitConceptId (@unitConceptName), the number and percent of records that have a value less than @plausibleValueLow.</i>	Verification	Plausibility	Atemporal
CONCEPT	plausibleValue High	<i>For the combination of CONCEPT_ID @conceptId (@conceptName) and UNIT_CONCEPT_ID @unitConceptId (@unitConceptName), the number and percent of records that have a value higher than @plausibleValueHigh.</i>	Verification	Plausibility	Atemporal
CONCEPT	plausibleGender	<i>For a CONCEPT_ID @conceptId (@conceptName), the number and percent of records associated with patients with an implausible gender (correct gender = @plausibleGender).</i>	Validation	Plausibility	Atemporal

2.3 Dashboard usage

Within the dashboard package is a set of [csv files](#) that dictate how the dashboard should be run and which thresholds should be applied to each data quality check. The ‘_Check_Descriptions.csv’ contains the data quality check types, their descriptions, and which SQL file is associated with each. They are then organized into table-level, field-level, and concept-level checks, each represented with its own csv file that detail which checks are run by placing a ‘Yes’ or ‘No’ in the corresponding cell. Each check has a threshold against which the resulting statistic of the check will be evaluated that can be pre-specified by writing the threshold value in the appropriate cell.

These files have a default structure that is set up to run approximately 3,351 checks using the systematic-based approach listed in the above section, taking anywhere from a few minutes to a few hours depending on database size. Ideally all checks would be run on every CDM instance but not all sites can populate every table (natural-language processing data is not always available, for instance). Fortunately, this underlying structure is customizable so that each SME and data partner can adjust which checks are run and how they are evaluated to meet their needs and reflect the aspects unique to their data. This includes turning off checks for CDM tables that are not populated or adjusting the evaluation thresholds. Perhaps only 10% of the records in a MEASUREMENT table have values and the threshold needs to be lowered to reflect that nuance of the data. Each change that is made is then communicated in the final output object.

It is important to note that it is not expected that the default threshold settings will work for every site that uses the DQD. That is why all of the checks that were run are included in the final output and why all pertinent information is captured including the numerator and the denominator.

Once the csv files are edited based on the SME or data partner’s needs an R package is called that reads in the csv files and applies the specifications to run the data quality checks. These results can be written to a table if so desired but the main output is a JSON object. This JSON object is then used by the Data Quality

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Dashboard shiny application viewer to display an interactive set of data quality results. A live demo of this application can be found [here](#).

Figure 1 shows the Overview page of the DQD. It shows a count of all data quality checks, both passed and failed, organized by Kahn category and context. This should be used as a way to understand potential weaknesses of the database and areas that should be investigated in the results section (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Data Quality Dashboard Overview Page

It is very important that some metadata about the CDM instance is conveyed along with the data quality results. Without a general understanding of the database, what population it represents, which OMOP Vocabulary version was used, etc., it is very difficult to interpret the results. Figure 2 shows the Metadata page of the DQD clearly communicating this information with the user. If this information is not present in the CDM_SOURCE table of the CDM, the Data Quality Dashboard will not produce results.

Figure 2: Data Quality Dashboard Metadata Page

While the Overview and Metadata pages are important to the overall understanding of the results, the real power of the DQD is in the results page. Each of three thousand data quality check that were run represents one row in the table. The status of the check (pass or fail), Kahn category, context, and subcategory are

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displayed along with the fully qualified description of the check and the percent of records that violated the rule that was run (figure 3).

SYNTHEA SYNTHETIC HEALTH DATABASE

OVERVIEW

METADATA

RESULTS

ABOUT

RESULTS

SYNTHEA SYNTHETIC HEALTH DATABASE

Results generated at 2019-08-22 14:15:06 in 29 mins

Show entries

Search:

STATUS	CONTEXT	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	LEVEL	DESCRIPTION	% RECORDS	
<input type="button" value="FAIL"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>			
<input type="button" value="⊕"/>	FAIL	Validation	Completeness	None	TABLE	The number and percent of persons in the CDM that do not have at least one record in the VISIT_OCCURRENCE table. (Threshold=0%).	66.96%
<input type="button" value="⊕"/>	FAIL	Verification	Completeness	None	FIELD	The number and percent of distinct source values in the race_source_value field of the PERSON table mapped to 0. (Threshold=0%).	50.00%
<input type="button" value="⊕"/>	FAIL	Verification	Conformance	Relational	FIELD	The number and percent of records that have a value in the person_id field in the OBSERVATION_PERIOD table that does not exist in the PERSON table. (Threshold=0%).	49.58%
<input type="button" value="⊕"/>	FAIL	Verification	Plausibility	Atemporal	FIELD	The number and percent of records with a value in the gap_days field of the DRUG_ERA table less than 0. (Threshold=0%).	24.07%
<input type="button" value="⊕"/>	FAIL	Verification	Completeness	None	FIELD	The number and percent of records with a value of 0 in the standard concept field race_concept_id in the PERSON table. (Threshold=0%).	16.74%

Showing 46 to 50 of 82 entries (filtered from 1,639 total entries)

Previous
1
...
9
10
11
...
17
Next

Figure 3: Data Quality Dashboard Results Page

Embedded in the description of each check is the pre-specified threshold that the result was compared to in order to determine the pass or fail status. If the percent of records that violated the check is equal to or higher than the threshold, the check is considered a failure. If the percent of records that violated the check is below the threshold, the check is considered passing. For more information about a data quality check, pass or fail, clicking the plus sign next to each will reveal the number of rows violating a rule along with the percentage that represents as well as the SQL query that was run to return those values (figure 4).

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SYNTHEA SYNTHETIC HEALTH DATABASE

Results generated at 2019-08-22 14:15:06 in 29 mins

Show entries Search:

STATUS	CONTEXT	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	LEVEL	DESCRIPTION	% RECORDS
FAIL	Validation	Completeness	None	TABLE	The number and percent of persons in the CDM that do not have at least one record in the VISIT_OCCURRENCE table (Threshold=0%).	66.96%

Name: measurePersonCompleteness

Description: The number and percent of persons in the CDM that do not have at least one record in the VISIT_OCCURRENCE table (Threshold=0%).

Level: TABLE

Rows Violated: 1804

% Rows Violated: 66.96%

Execution Time: 7.510152 secs

SQL Query: /*****
Table Level:
MEASURE_PERSON_COMPLETENESS
Determine what #/% of persons have at least one record in the cdmTable

Parameters used in this template:
cdmDatabaseSchema = cdm_synthesa_v097.dbo
cdmTableName = VISIT_OCCURRENCE

Figure 4: Data Quality Dashboard Extended Results

This interactive way to explore data quality makes it accessible and easy to understand where the values reported are being generated.

2.4 Implementation

Each SME and data partner will be expected to run the Data Quality Dashboard on the data at their site once it is converted to the OMOP CDM. Initially it can be used to assess whether OMOP Standards such as primary key constraints and concept domain restrictions are being followed. Thinking specifically of the EHDEN federated network, providing an interactive data quality report for each participating site will provide evidence not only that ETL processes were done correctly but also to demonstrate that the necessary due diligence was done to ensure that the data are of research quality.

3. CONCLUSION

The Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) developed as part of EHDEN Work Package 4 provides a comprehensive, customizable, and transparent way to both evaluate and communicate the quality of an OMOP CDM instance. The widely accepted Kahn Framework for data quality was chosen to organize the checks types. We believe the DQD is a strong foundation for data quality reporting, and a key tool to ensure confidence in the evidence generated through the EHDEN federated network.

4. NEXT STEPS

Following the work that was done to develop version 1 of the Data Quality Dashboard, a number of items were identified as potential next steps for version 2.

	D4.2 - First version of the Framework for quality benchmarking		
	WP4 – Technical Infrastructure	Version: v2.0 – final	
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Maxim Moinat, Michel van Speybroeck	Security: PU	17/17

- Easier process for adding data quality checks. The current process for adding checks includes manipulation of the R code. An easier process should be developed so it is merely a matter of adding a new check to the csv files.
- Allow the DQD to be run on a cohort instead of the entire database. When approaching data quality from a study perspective, often it is more important to understand the quality of data for a particular cohort than for the whole database.
- Develop a way to visualize data quality results across a network. The shiny application currently only shows the DQD results from one database. It would be helpful to see the results of a network of databases so that they can be compared.
- Collaborate with the OHDSI community to extend the list of data quality check types.

5. REFERENCES

1. Kahn, M.G., et al., *A Harmonized Data Quality Assessment Terminology and Framework for the Secondary Use of Electronic Health Record Data*. EGEMS (Wash DC), 2016. 4(1): p. 1244.